

1. Southern analysis of one ITA212 hygromycin-resistant callus line (C) and regenerated plant (P). DNA was either undigested (UD) or digested by *Not1*, *Sac1*, or *Kpn1*. The *Not1* sites are flanking the 2-kb *CaMV35S*-promoter-*aphIV*-NOS-poly A sequence in pWRG4517Δ86 plasmid and only one *Sac1* site is present in this plasmid. Nontransformed (NT) and previously obtained transformed (T) rice plants (Christou et al 1991) were used as negative and positive controls, respectively. The membrane was hybridized with the *aphIV* gene.

2. Western blot of an SDS PAGE gel probed with a polyclonal antibody raised to oryzacystatin Oc-I (Urwin et al 1995). Lanes 1-3 were loaded with 2 µg total protein from ITA212-transformed rice plants regenerated from three independent lines. Lanes 4-8 were loaded with 2 µg total protein from an ITA212-untransformed rice plant to which 0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, or 1% Oc-I protein was added.

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An improved biolistic method for transformation and production of fertile transgenic Pusa Basmati rice plants

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An improved biolistic procedure for the transformation of embryogenic suspension cells of Pusa Basmati 1 (aromatic, fine grained, semidwarf plant type, Group 1 indica), has been developed. The procedure involves using of suitable reporter or other useful genes, osmotic preconditioning of cells on a medium supplemented with 0.25 M mannitol prior to bombardment, gold particles for DNA delivery, and plant regeneration medium with high agarose concentration (1.0%). This procedure allowed us to produce more than 600 transient transformants and 12-50 fertile transgenic plants per bombarded filter carrying 0.5 mL settled cell volume (scv) of rice cells.

We have been working on biolistic transformation of Basmati rice (Pusa Basmati 1) using gene constructs that can potentially improve the defense against insect attack and water stress tolerance. Pusa Basmati 1 is an improved, fine grain, aromatic, and semidwarf indica rice variety that essentially belongs to Varietal Group 1 (Jain et al 1995). Plasmids carrying β-

glucuronidase (GUS) gene or other agronomically important genes driven by the actin 1 gene promoter (*Act1*), were constructed for rice transformation. Act1F-GUS plasmid (McElroy et al 1990) was used for transient gene expression studies; other plasmids carrying potato protease inhibitor 2 (*PIN2*) gene, or a late embryogenesis-abundant protein (*Lea3*) gene from barley (see figure), were used for optimization of the biolistic process and production of useful transgenic plants. The structure of these plasmids is shown in the figure.

In the beginning, we used the biolistic japonica rice transformation procedure developed in this laboratory (Cao et al 1992) for DNA delivery into Pusa Basmati 1 cells. The procedure involved bombardment of M10 tungsten particles coated with plasmid DNA using the DuPont Helium PDS-1000 device keeping the bombardment pressure of 1500 psi, gap distance (distance between the rupture disc and the launch point of macroprojectile) of 1.0 cm, and target cell distance (distance between the target cells and the launch point of the microprojectiles) of 12 cm. Each filter, carrying 0.5 mL scv of suspension cells, was bombarded twice with tungsten particles coated with 2.5 µg plasmid DNA. This procedure produced per filter paper an average of 24 blue spots (transient transformants, see table, line 1) or 4.0-6.8 ammonium glufosinate-resistant (*AG^R*) calli (see table, lines 6 and 12). For practical plant genetic transformation work, at least several hundred potentially generated cells

Structure of pAct1F-GUS, pBY520 and pTWa plasmids. Act1 5', rice actin 1 gene promoter; **Act1 In**, intron from Act1 5' promoter region; **bar**, phosphinothricin acetyl transferase gene; **HVA1**, late embryogenesis abundant (LEA3) protein gene; **Nos3'**, nopaline synthase gene 3' region; **Pin2**, potato protease inhibitor 2 gene; **Pin2 3'**, **Pin2 3'** region; **Pin2 5'**, **Pin2** promoter region; **35S 5'**, cauliflower mosaic virus 35S promoter. Only important restriction endonuclease sites are indicated.

Effect of metallic particles, osmotic preconditioning of cells, and target cell distance on GUS expression and stable transformation in Pusa Basmati 1 cells.^a

Plasmid	Osmotic preconditioning ^b	Particle type	Target cell distance (cm)	Number of blue spots ^c or resistant calli ^d per filter	
pAct1F-Gus	No	Tungsten	12, 12	24.4 ± 5.2 ^c	
	No	Tungsten	9, 9	37.3 ± 8.4 ^c	
	Yes	Tungsten	12, 12	207.8 ± 27.8 ^c	
	Yes	Tungsten	9, 9	215.0 ± 41.5 ^c	
	No	Gold	12, 12	132.5 ± 25.8 ^c	
	No	Gold	9, 9	158.7 ± 16.5 ^c	
	Yes	Gold	12, 12	510.3 ± 142.1 ^c	
	Yes	Gold	9, 9	684.8 ± 91.1 ^c	
pTWa	No	Tungsten	12, 12	6.8 ± 1.4 ^d	
	No	Tungsten	9, 9	14.4 ± 4.4 ^d	
	No	Tungsten	9, 12	13.3 ± 1.9 ^d	
	No	Gold	9, 12	27.0 ± 4.6 ^d	
	Yes	Tungsten	9, 12	43.3 ± 0.6 ^d	
	Yes	Gold	9, 12	102.7 ± 25.0 ^d	
pLEA3	No	Tungsten	12, 12	4.0 ± 4.4 ^d	
	No	Tungsten	9, 9	10.8 ± 1.2 ^d	
	No	Tungsten	9, 12	10.7 ± 1.6 ^d	
	No	Gold	9, 12	24.5 ± 3.4 ^d	
	Yes	Tungsten	9, 12	24.1 ± 4.7 ^d	
	Yes	Gold	9, 12	52.7 ± 8.5 ^d	

^aData represent the mean ± standard error of three independent experiments. For each experiment, three filters were used and the values averaged. ^bFilters carrying target cells were kept on the MS2.5 medium supplemented with 0.25 M mannitol for 24 h before bombardment. ^cNumber of blue spots per filter. ^dNumber of ammonium glufoisinate-resistant calli per filter.

should receive and transiently express the introduced DNA per bombardment (Yang and Christou 1994). To improve transformation frequencies, we investigated the effects of osmotic preconditioning of cells, metallic nature of microcarriers, and target cell distance on transformation of Pusa Basmati 1 cells (data presented in the table). The optimal conditions of each parameter were then combined to form a new improved protocol.

The new improved protocol. Cell suspension cultures of Pusa Basmati 1 were established using the mature seed scutella-derived calli, as described by Jain et al (1995). Plasmid DNAs were adsorbed to the gold or tungsten particles (mean diameter of 1 µm, Sylvania-GTE Products Corp., Towanda, PA) by CaCl₂ and spermidine precipitation and bombarded to the target cells (Cao et al 1992). To prepare filters with competent cells, 0.5 mL scv of sieved (1000 µm nylon mesh) suspension cells obtained after 4 d of subculture were spread on each of the 5.5-cm-diameter Whatman #1 filter disc. For osmotic preconditioning, the filter discs were placed on the surface of 25 mL of 0.5% (w/v) agarose-solidified Murashige and Skoog (1962) medium with 2.5 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹ (MS2.5) and 0.25 M mannitol in 9-cm petri dishes. These dishes were used for the biolistic experiment the following day.

Each filter disc was bombarded twice with the metallic particles coated with 2.5 µg of plasmid DNA, sequentially keeping the target cell distances of 9 and 12 cm in the first and second bombardment. Microscopic observations showed that the bombardments made using the two different target cell distances allowed a more even distribution of coated-particles to cells, with minimum damage to the cells. After 24 h, filters were transferred to the new dishes containing mannitol-free MS2.5 medium. Histochemical GUS expression assay was carried out 2 d after bombardment (Battraw and Hall 1990). Blue loci, indicative of transient GUS expression, were counted 2 d after adding the X-Gluc substrate solution.

Three days after the bombardment, filter discs with overlaying cells were transferred to the petri dishes containing 25 ml MS2.5 medium supplemented with 8 mg L⁻¹ ammonium glufosinate for selecting transformed calli. These filters were transferred every 10 d onto the fresh selection medium. Petri dishes were always sealed with the parafilm and incubated at 26 °C in the dark. After 30-40 d, the new calli showing active cell proliferation on the selection medium and growing up about 1.0 cm diameters (referred to as resistant calli), were transferred to the MS-based regeneration medium containing maltose (30 g L⁻¹), kinetin (2.0 mg L⁻¹), *a*-naphthalene acetic acid [NAA] (0.5 mg L⁻¹), ammonium glufosinate (5.0 mg L⁻¹); the medium was solidified with 1.0% agarose. For plant regeneration, cultures were incubated at 26 °C in the dark for 2 wk and then transferred to light (55 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹, daylight fluorescent tubes, 16-h photoperiod). After 4 wk, these calli were transferred onto regeneration medium with lower concentrations of agarose (0.5%, w/v) and ammonium glufosinate (3 mg L⁻¹). Regenerated shoots were transferred to the rooting medium (0.25%, w/v phytigel-

solidified MS medium with 1.5 mg NAA L⁻¹) and 4 wk later, they were transferred to pots in the greenhouse.

This new procedure produced an average of 510-684 transient transformants and 24-103 transformed AG^R calli per filter; the number of transformants was higher using gold particles and with pT_{Wa} plasmid (see table). Water stress created by using higher agarose concentration (1.0% instead of 0.5%) promoted somatic embryogenesis, and shoot regeneration frequencies of 69-91% were obtained from AG^R calli. A total of 235 plants obtained after transformation with the two plasmids were analyzed by PCR using a suitable set of primers derived from the promoter, *bar* or *PIN2* gene sequences. As an internal control, a set of primers that amplify a 304-bp product during PCR from *Act1* promoter region was used. Of these, 188 plants showed the amplification of expected size of DNA fragment, indicating that 80% of selected AG^R plants are true transgenic plants. All the transformed plants transferred to the greenhouse were fertile and showed good seed set within 110-145 d after planting. Further molecular and progeny analyses of these transgenic plants are in progress.

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Genetic analysis of a d1 chimeric rice plant

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A chimeric rice plant has been maintained through seed for more than 50 yr in our laboratory. It has both normal and dwarf tillers. The dwarf tillers have wide dark green leaves, short panicles, and small round grains. Differences in chimeric manifestations were observed in chimeric plants (see figure). Both the dwarf-type progenies and dwarf tillers of the chimeric plant

are short, with wide dark green leaves, short panicles, and small round grains. These characters are almost the same as the Daikoku dwarf carrying the *d1* gene. We therefore call the chimeric plants d1 chimeric type.

Progenies of both the dwarf and normal tillers of the chimeric plant were dwarf, chimeric, or normal (see figure). To test the inheritance of the chimeric expression, dwarf and normal plants obtained from chimeric plants were crossed. The 26 F₁ hybrids produced by crossing a dwarf plant with a normal plant were all normal. Furthermore, 18 and 34 F₁ hybrids from crosses of dwarf and normal tillers of chimeric plants with IR24 and Taichung 65 were all normal. Segregation in F₂ from the

reciprocal crosses of the dwarf plants with IR24, Taichung 65, and the normal plant segregated into 3 normal:1 dwarf (see table). The results indicate a single recessive gene controls chimeric expression of the d1 chimeric plant.

To test for allelism between d1 and the d1 chimeric plants, dwarf plants obtained from the chimeric plant were crossed to a genetic marker carrying the *d1* gene. Seventeen F₁ hybrids from the reciprocal crosses of *d1*/dwarf plant were all *d1*-like plants, indicating that chimeric locus is allelic to the *d1* locus.

High frequency mutation at the *d1* locus could cause the occurrence of a d1 chimeric plant. When the three types of progenies from the plant were selfed, the average frequency of chimeric type